

CREEP MECHANISMS IN DISCONTINUOUSLY-REINFORCED CERAMIC COMPOSITES

David S. Wilkinson

Department of Materials Science and Engineering
McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario L8S 4L7, Canada

ABSTRACT

The creep behaviour of discontinuously-reinforced ceramic matrix composites, in which the volume fraction of the harder (reinforcing) phase may range widely between zero and one, can be understood by recourse to rheological models, provided that the nature of the particle percolation behaviour in the composite system is understood. Two percolation thresholds have been identified, corresponding to point contacts and to full-facet contacts between particles. In this short paper, the approach developed to understand this behaviour is reviewed and the models which have been developed are briefly described.

PERCOLATION THRESHOLDS IN TWO PHASE COMPOSITES

We start by considering the nature of the percolation process in two phase systems consisting of discrete particles embedded in a matrix. At low volume fraction ϕ , particles are well dispersed and only a few particles are in contact with one another. As the particle volume fraction rises the number of these contacts increases (Fig. 1) until, at the percolation threshold ϕ_{pcp} , point contacts between particles percolate throughout the material. For spherical particles of uniform size this occurs at a volume fraction of about 16 vol% [1]. However, for non-equiaxed particles such as whiskers or platelets the percolation threshold moves to much smaller volume fractions. Thus, Nan [2] has shown that for whiskers with high aspect ratio λ , the point-contact percolation threshold is equal to $0.7/\lambda$. For example, with an aspect ratio of 40, ϕ_{pcp} is reduced to about 2 vol%. Therefore network effects will significantly influence the creep behaviour of whisker- and platelet-reinforced ceramics. Moreover, the processing of these materials is also complicated by the development of network forces [3, 4].

Figure 1: A schematic illustration of point-contact percolation for the case of whiskers.

Figure 2: A schematic illustration of facet-contact percolation. The inset illustrates the thin film of material which coats all grain boundaries.

In the case of reinforcing materials such as whiskers or platelets the formation of a highly interconnected network beyond ϕ_{pcp} limits the volume fraction of the reinforcing phase to about 40%. However, it is possible to make materials in which a very high volume fraction of a hard phase is embedded in a continuous soft matrix. A classic example of this type is that of the cemented carbides. In terms of ceramics, such materials include siliconized silicon carbide and glass-bonded silicon

nitride. In these materials phase transformations occur during processing which enable a large volume fraction of the hard phase to develop. This is possible because the new phase which forms is highly faceted, as illustrated schematically in Fig. 2, and therefore particles can be packed to high volume fraction. In the silicon nitride case for example, the starting α -Si₃N₄ particles dissolve into the liquid phase which forms during sintering and then reprecipitate as β -Si₃N₄. The volume fraction of the amorphous phase which remains after cooling from the sintering temperature can be as low as 5%. Nonetheless it forms a continuous phase which wets all the grain boundaries with a film 1-2 nm in thickness. These materials exhibit a form of connectivity which we have called "facet-contact percolation" [5, 6], as illustrated in Fig. 2. The volume fraction at which this form of percolation first appears ϕ_{fcp} has yet to be determined analytically. However, it is thought to be around 64% [7]. It is worthy of note that particles do not need actually to touch in order to form a network of either type. Even when there is a thin film of the matrix phase separating the hard particles, the constraints develop in such a way that the flow of the material is expected to be quite different from that of an unpercolated composite.

This classification of microstructures into three regimes (I: $\phi < \phi_{pcp}$, II: $\phi_{pcp} < \phi < \phi_{fcp}$, and III: $\phi > \phi_{fcp}$) can be used to help model the creep behaviour of a wide range of multi-phase ceramic materials. This is described briefly in the following section.

MODELS FOR CREEP

LOW VOLUME FRACTION REGIME

We can model the creep behaviour of a composite containing a dilute dispersion of hard particles using the geometry shown in Fig. 3. The overall viscosity of the composite is given by

$$\eta = \eta_0 (1 + 2.5 \phi) \quad (1)$$

which is identical to the classic result of Einstein [8, 9] for the viscosity of a fluid containing a dilute particle suspension. Here η_0 is the viscosity of the unreinforced matrix material.

HIGH VOLUME FRACTION REGIME

Somewhat surprisingly the creep of composites containing a high volume fraction of particles ($\phi > \phi_{pcp}$) can also be modeled to an adequate level of precision using the geometry of Fig. 3. This is because at high volume fraction the particles are locked in place and cannot undergo significant translation with respect to each other (assuming that the hard phase is sufficiently rigid). Under the application of a remote stress material in the deformable film around the sphere migrates and the overall rheological behaviour of the composite can be determined* [5, 10]. The result of such a calculation, which is presented in detail elsewhere [11], yields

$$\eta = \eta_0 \frac{10.8}{(1 - \phi)^3} \quad (2)$$

*This is actually an over simplification, in that it ignores other mechanisms, such as cavitation and dissolution/reprecipitation creep, which can contribute significantly to the creep of this class of materials. A more complete analysis of these processes is presented elsewhere.

which suggests a rather sensitive dependence on the remaining volume fraction of the matrix phase, $1-\phi$. A series of geometrically more exact models have been developed based on two-dimensional arrays of hexagonal grains [11, 12] and on three-dimensional arrays of rectangular-prism-shaped grains [13]. In each case the grains are assumed to be separated by a soft phase which is initially of uniform thickness. These models produce remarkably similar results which differ only in terms of the numerical constant and a dependence on the particle aspect ratio. Therefore in a typical silicon nitride ceramic in which the grain boundary films are of order 2 nm thick and the grain size is about 1 μm , the "effective" volume fraction of the soft phase (which we define as the volume fraction of the glass residing at the grain boundaries) is about $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Equation (2) indicates that the effective viscosity of these materials should therefore be about 9 orders of magnitude greater than that of the glass itself. Thus, while the amorphous phase controls the creep of the material, the rheology of flow has a dramatic effect on the overall rate.

INTERMEDIATE VOLUME FRACTION REGIME

The situation at intermediate volume fractions ($\phi_{\text{pcp}} < \phi < \phi_{\text{fcP}}$) is more complex. In this regime the particles form a network but with sufficient freedom of motion that some rotation and bending of the particles are possible. The materials of practical interest in this regime are primarily whisker-reinforced ceramics, and there is now a substantial body of experimental data on the creep behaviour of these materials, primarily SiC-reinforced Al_2O_3 [14-28], but also other systems [29-33]. Briefly, these data suggest that whiskers decrease the creep rate by about two orders of magnitude. This effect appears to be only weakly dependent on the volume fraction of whiskers added, especially in the range between 15 and 30%. However, there are numerous complicating features related to the effects of whisker additions on processing which must be carefully accounted for in assessing this data.

Recently, attempts have been made to model the creep response of a whisker network embedded in a matrix [34]. These models assume that the whiskers are primarily aligned in a plane, as illustrated schematically in Fig. 4. This is consistent with the orientation achieved during hot pressing. Two mechanisms are envisaged. The first, termed viscoelastic creep, is based on the elastic bending of whiskers at points of contact. Such bending will be accommodated by matrix creep thus limiting the rate of deformation. Eventually however, the network will relax to a configuration in which the whiskers bear all of the load and creep stops. If the load is subsequently removed (while still at high temperature) the whiskers will tend to relax back to a stress-free state. Thus this process should lead to significant anelastic strains similar to those observed experimentally in both SiC-whisker reinforced Al_2O_3 [28, 35] and Si_3N_4 [36]. The effective viscosity of a composite controlled by this mechanism is given by

$$\eta_{ve} = \eta_o \frac{16}{(f\phi)^{1/3} \cdot \sin 2\theta} \quad (3)$$

where f is a term which describes the packing efficiency of the whiskers in the composite [34], and θ is the angle of average misalignment of the whiskers from the direction of the applied tensile stress. The maximum strain which is achievable by this process is

$$\epsilon_{\text{max}} = \frac{16}{\phi^{2/3} f^{5/3}} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{E} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: A hard spherical particle contained in a deformable spherical shell provides a useful model for flow in composites containing either a dilute dispersion or a high volume fraction of the hard phase.

Figure 4: The idealized microstructure used to model creep in a whisker-reinforced ceramic composite. The average whisker spacing is assumed to be greater within each plane ($2l$) than between planes ($2w$) as a result of hot pressing.

where σ is the far-field applied stress and E is the composite modulus.

The second mechanism which has been modeled has been termed viscoplastic creep. In this case we assume that at many contacts between whiskers some matrix material remains. As deformation proceeds this material is squeezed from these regions of near contact until the structure becomes locked in place. The initial viscosity due to this process is given by

$$\eta_{vp} = \eta_o \frac{4(1+f)}{\lambda^2 f \sin 2\theta} \left[\left(\frac{f^2}{\Phi} \right) - 1 \right]^{-3} \quad (5)$$

This process is also transient in nature since it ceases once all of the matrix material is removed from

the near-contact regions. The resistance to viscoplastic flow depends critically on the packing efficiency f since this determines the spacing between whiskers parallel to the hot pressing direction. The packing efficiency has a minimum value of $f_{\min} = \sqrt{\phi}$, which corresponds to continuous contact between the whisker planes parallel to the hot pressing direction.

These models can be used to develop a map of the creep response. An example is shown in Fig. 5. Here the volume fraction ϕ is plotted as a function of the packing efficiency f . A constant whisker aspect ratio of 10 is assumed in this example, along with a misorientation of 10° . Contours of constant effective viscosity η/η_0 are plotted on the diagram.

Figure 5: A creep mechanism map for an aligned whisker-reinforced composite.

The diagram shows three regimes. The upper left corner of the diagram corresponds to impossible microstructures. The boundary of this region, corresponding to $f_{\min} = \sqrt{\phi}$, yields the most creep resistant microstructures in which only viscoelastic creep is possible, with the effective creep viscosity $\eta \sim 1/\phi$. In other words the models actually predict a decrease in viscosity as the volume fraction of whiskers is increased. This is because the spacing between contacts which controls the diffusion distance is reduced. For values of f close to but greater than f_{\min} the results are complex, but suggest that only a weak dependence on volume fraction should be found, consistent with experiment. The map also suggests that relative viscosities of 10 to 40 should be achievable for these conditions, of the same order as that observed experimentally.

SUMMARY

Two phase microstructures consisting of hard particles embedded in a relatively soft matrix can be fabricated with the volume fraction of the hard phase varying over the complete range from zero to almost one. Three distinct microstructural regimes can be identified according to the nature of interparticle percolation. This is related to two separate percolation processes. The first based on point contact between particles is relatively well understood and the percolation threshold can be calculated, at least for well-defined particle shapes (essentially those showing spheroidal symmetry). The second is based on facet contacts and requires that particles are angular in shape and accommodate

to each other during fabrication, usually due to in-situ phase transformations during the densification process. Below the limit for point-contact percolation, the creep resistance is given by the Einstein equation, or its extension for elongated particles. At high volume fraction, above the threshold for facet-contact percolation, creep is thought to be controlled by the flow of the softer phase in the regions between the particles. Models developed for this process suggest that creep is sensitive to the thickness of the interparticle films, which in some materials are of nanometre dimensions. At intermediate volume fractions, corresponding to whisker-reinforced ceramics two mechanisms have been identified and modeled. One is based on a viscous flow process similar to that which dominates creep at high volume fraction, but localized in the regions of near-contact between the whiskers. A second mechanism is based on the elastic bending of the whiskers accommodated by matrix creep. A mechanism map for this regime has been developed which is at least in qualitative agreement with experimental observations.

REFERENCES

1. D. M. Grannan, J. C. Garland and D. B. Tanner, "Critical Behaviour of the Dielectric Constant of a Random Composite Near the Percolation Threshold", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, **46** 375-78 (1981).
2. C.-W. Nan, "Physics of Inhomogeneous Inorganic Materials", *Prog. Mater. Sci.*, **37** 1-116 (1993).
3. F. F. Lange, "Constrained Network Model for Predicting Densification Behaviour of Composite Powders", *J. Mater. Res.*, **2** 59-65 (1987).
4. F. F. Lange, D. C. C. Lam, O. Sudre, B. D. Flinn, C. Folsom, B. V. Velamakanni, F. W. Zok and A. G. Evans, "Powder Processing of Ceramic Matrix Composites", *Mater. Sci. Engin.*, **A144** 143-52 (1991).
5. D. S. Wilkinson, "Creep Mechanisms in Multi-Phase Ceramic Materials: A Feature Article", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, in preparation (1995).
6. D. S. Wilkinson, "Creep Mechanisms in Multi-Phase Ceramics", in *Plastic Deformation of Ceramics*. Edited by J. L. Routbort, C. Brookes and R. Bradt. (Plenum, NY, 1994), in press.
7. I. Balberg, "Recent Developments in Continuum Percolation", *Phil. Mag. B*, **56** 991-1003 (1987).
8. A. Einstein, "Eine neue bestimmung der molekuledimensionen", *Annalen der Physik* (4), **19**, 289-306, (1906)
9. A. Einstein, *Annalen der Physik* (4), **34**, 591-2 (1911); correction to *Annalen der Physik* (4), **19**, 289-306 (English translation of corrected version in *Investigations into the Theory of Brownian Motion* by Albert Einstein, Dover Publications Inc., (New York, 1956), 36-62)
10. D. S. Wilkinson, "Creep Mechanisms in Silicon Nitride Ceramics", p.327-338 in *Tailoring of High Temperature Properties of Si₃N₄ Ceramics*. Edited by M. J. Hoffmann and G. Petzow. Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 1994.
11. J. R. Dryden, D. Kucеровsky, D. S. Wilkinson and D. F. Watt, "Creep Deformation Due to a Viscous Grain Boundary Phase", *Acta metall.*, **37** 2007-15 (1989).
12. M. M. Chadwick, D. S. Wilkinson and J. R. Dryden, "Creep Due to a Non-Newtonian Grain Boundary Phase", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **75** 2327-34 (1992).
13. D. S. Wilkinson and J. R. Dryden, "The Effect of Grain Anisotropy On Creep By Viscous Flow", to be published (1995).
14. A. H. Choksi and J. R. Porter, "Creep Deformation of an Alumina Matrix Composite Reinforced With Silicon Carbide Whiskers", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **68** C144-155 (1985).
15. J. R. Porter, F. F. Lange and A. H. Choksi, "Processing and Creep Performance of SiC-Whisker Reinforced Al₂O₃", *Bull. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **66** 343-47 (1987).
16. P. F. Becher and T. N. Tiegs, "Temperature Dependence of Strengthening By Whisker Reinforcement: SiC Whisker-Reinforced Alumina in Air", *Adv. Ceram. Mater.*, **3** 148-53 (1988).
17. K. Y. Donaldson, A. Venkateswaran, D. P. H. Hasselman and J. F. Rhodes, "Speculation On the Creep Behaviour of Silicon Carbide Whisker-Reinforced Alumina", *Ceram. Engin. & Sci. Proc.*,

- 10 (9-10) 1191-1211 (1989).
18. M. Backhaus-Ricoult, J. Castaing and J. L. Routbort, "Creep of SiC-Whisker Reinforced Si₃N₄", *Revue Phys. Appl.*, **23** 239-49 (1988).
 19. J. L. Routbort, K. C. Goretta, A. Domínguez-Rodríguez and A. R. de Arellano-López, "Creep of Whisker-Reinforced Ceramics", *J. Hard Mater.*, **1** 221-32 (1990).
 20. H. T. Lin and P. F. Becher, "Creep Behaviour of a SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Alumina", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **73** 1378-81 (1990).
 21. H. T. Lin and P. F. Becher, "High-Temperature Creep Deformation of Alumina-SiC-Whisker Composites", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **74** 1886-93 (1991).
 22. A. R. de Arellano-López, F. L. Cumbreza, A. Domínguez-Rodríguez, K. C. Goretta and J. L. Routbort, "Compressive Creep of SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Al₂O₃", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **73** 1297-1300 (1990).
 23. P. Lipetzky, S. R. Nutt, D. A. Koester and R. F. Davis, "Atmospheric Effects On Compressive Creep of SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Alumina", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **74** 1240-47 (1991).
 24. H. T. Lin and P. F. Becher, "Grain Size Effect On Creep Deformation of Alumina-SiC Composites", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **76** submitted (1994).
 25. A. R. de Arellano-López, A. Domínguez-Rodríguez, K. C. Goretta and J. L. Routbort, "Plastic Deformation Mechanisms in SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Al₂O₃", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **76** 1425-32 (1993).
 26. A. R. de Arellano-López, A. Domínguez-Rodríguez, K. C. Goretta and J. L. Routbort, "Influence of Fabrication On Mechanical Properties of SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Alumina", *Proc. 1991 European Ceramic Society Conference* (1993).
 27. W. Gu, J. R. Porter and T. G. Langdon, "Evidence for Anelastic Creep Recovery in Silicon Carbide-Whisker-Reinforced Alumina", *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **77** 1679-81 (1994).
 28. W. Gu, J. R. Porter and T. G. Langdon, "Anelastic Creep Recovery of Alumina Reinforced With SiC Whiskers of Particulates", in *Ceramic Matrix Composites*. American Ceramic Society, Westerville, OH, USA, 1994.
 29. R. D. Nixon, S. Chevacharoenkul, R. F. Davis and T. N. Tiegs, "Creep of Hot-Pressed SiC Whisker Reinforced Mullite", *Ceram. Trans.*, **6** 579-603 (1990).
 30. S. M. Wiederhorn, R. J. Gettings, D. E. Roberts, C. Ostertag and J. J. Petrovic, "Tensile Creep of Silicide Composites", *Mater. Sci. Engin.*, **A155** 209-15 (1992).
 31. K. Sadananda, C. R. Feng, H. Jones and J. J. Petrovic, "Creep of Molybdenum Disilicide Composites", *Mater. Sci. Engin.*, **A155** 227-39 (1992).
 32. P. Wang, G. Grathwol and F. Thümmeler, "Creep Behaviour of SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ Composites", *Powder Metall. Inter.*, **24** 365-72 (1992).
 33. M. Backhaus-Ricoult and P. Eveno, "Creep Properties of an Alumina-Zirconia Composite Reinforced With Silicon Carbide Whiskers", *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, **11** 51-62 (1993).
 34. D. S. Wilkinson and W. Pompe, "Models for Creep in Whisker- And Platelet-Reinforced Ceramics", to be published (1995).
 35. J. R. Porter, "Observation of Non-Steady State Creep in Whisker Reinforced Alumina", pp. 147-52 in *Whisker- and Fiber-Toughened Ceramics*. Edited by R. A. Bradley, D. E. Clark, D. C. Larsen and J. O. Steigler. ASM International, Metals Park, OH, 1988.
 36. S. Haig, W. R. Cannon and P. J. Whalen, "Anelastic Recovery in Crept Silicon Nitride", *Ceram. Engin. & Sci. Proc.*, **13** (9-10) 1008 (1992).